

Amelioration of High Temperature Stress in Crop Plants Employing Thermo-tolerant Microbes

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Summary

Incidences of high temperature stress impacting crop productivity across the world. Extreme events such as global warming, heat waves, prolonged water deficit condition are likely to further increase in the coming future due to climate change. A wide range of adaptation and mitigation strategies required to cope with high temperature stress. Efficient resource management practices and development of better crop breeds can help to overcome the heat stress tolerance to some extent. However, resource management and crop improvement strategies being long drawn and cost intensive, there is a need to develop simple and low-cost biological methods for the management of thermal stress. In respect to thermo-tolerant mechanism, Microorganisms could play a significant role for sustainable crop production. Some microbial symbionts are involved to mediate plant stress response through enhancing thermal-tolerance. Several meta-analysis studies in response to thermal stress tolerance found to be higher biomass and photosynthesis under heat stress conditions. Some studies revealed that significantly decreased accumulation of malondialdehyde (MDA) and hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) indicated a lower oxidation level in the colonized plants, which was also correlated with the higher activity of catalase, peroxidase, and glutathione reductase enzymes due to microbial colonization under heat stress.

Introduction

Constant rise of the ambient temperature due to continuous climate change is one of the worldwide issues and has devastating impact on the sustainable crop production (IPCC, 2019). Thermal stress causes adverse impact on the growth, development and physiological mechanism on the plants (Hassan et al., 2021). Thermal-stress is the serious threat responsible for crop loss across the world. Various measures have been standardized and can be taken to reduce the effect of thermal-stress. Plants develop varying levels of adaptation, avoidance, acclimatization, and tolerance mechanisms to cope with thermal-stress through morphological, physiological, biochemical, and molecular strategies. The atmospheric temperature higher than normal range leads to cascade of cellular function and release heat shock proteins (HSPs) that help to minimize the loss of plants at cellular level. The role of microbes on plant stress in response to thermal-stress has been given attention in last few years (Zhao, et al., 2021). In Several studies, it has

found that some plant species associated with microbial symbionts may influence responses of the host plant to thermal-stress. Microbes associated with plant thermal-stress tolerance are ubiquitous and pay attention in plant ecology and physiology (Dastogeer, et al., 2020). Moreover, microbes produce the wide range of compounds to impact the responses of plants at the molecular level, triggering the biosynthesis of pigments, secondary metabolites, hormones, antioxidants, and alkaloids (Naamala and Smith, 2021).

Thermo-tolerant Microbes

Thermo-tolerant microbes are biological agents associated with heat-tolerance mechanism. Several microbes have been identified to cause thermo-tolerance. Thermo-tolerance is the complex mechanism achieved by production of proline and glycine betaine. Proline and glycine betaine are the two compounds which contributes to thermoregulation. Exopolysaccharides are one of the biological substances released by bacterium under heat stress condition containing 97% water, which improve the moisture content in the soil (Ali, et al., 2020). Endophytes are Plant Growth-Promoting Rhizobacteria is the two identified thermo-tolerant microbes actively involved in the thermo-regulation under high-temperature stressed condition (Shekhawat, et al., 2022).

Endophytes are microbes used as biostimulants to produce compounds involved in the development of tolerance against heat stress. Most of the endophytes symbiotically are associated with plant cell and mediate heat stress mitigation. The modes of action of the endophytes for promoting growth under heat – stress have been reported by many researchers (Mukhtar, et al., 2022). Park et al., (2017) reported the effects of endophytic microbe *SA187* on *Arabidopsis thaliana* and wheat plants and he found that *Enterobacter sp. SA187* induced thermo-tolerance in plants by promoting thermo-priming.

Plant Growth-Promoting Rhizobacteria (PGPR) is another bacterium which promotes plant growth under heat stress through colonizing roots of plants. Plant Growth-Promoting Rhizobacteria promotes plant growth directly or indirectly. They promote plant growth directly by regulation nitrogen fixation, phosphate solubilisation and by accelerating the synthesis of plant growth regulators like Indole-3 acetic acid, gibberellic acid and cytokinin under heat stressed condition. Indirectly, they also promote plant growth under heat stress by producing proline, sugars, organic acids, and glycine betaine (Basu, et al., 2021).

Role of Thermo-tolerant microbes under thermal-stress

Thermo-tolerant microbes induced physiological changes such as photosynthesis, respiration, stomatal closure under heat-stress condition. They also mitigate heat-stress through nitrogen fixation, production of enzyme ACC-deaminase and phytohormones.

Thermal–stress breaks photosynthetic pigments and inhibits the proper growth and development of plants. Studies revealed that heat–stress condition inhibited RuBP production involved in the electron transport chains. Enzymes involved in the metabolic processes in photosystem are also inactivated when plant subjected to thermal–stress is the major cause of the lowering of photosynthesis (Qu, et al., 2021). Some oxygenic microbe’s (cyanobacteria) having light-harvesting have been identified and played crucial role under heat–stress during convert light energy into chemical energy through photosynthesis. Respiratory mechanism of the plants is also influenced under high temperature. Plant and beneficial microbe interaction minimized stress level and promote plant growth by maintaining nitrogen, hydrogen, sulphur, and oxygen levels in a biogeochemical cycle (Scafaro, et al., 2021).Stomatal conductance is one of the important physiological mechanisms of the green plants enhanced under high temperature by accelerating water loss through transpiration. Plant–microbial interaction enhances the production of abscisic acid (ABA), which causes stomatal closure to protect plants from water loss (Bharath, et al., 2021).

The process of conversion of gaseous N₂ is into biological forms of NH₃ and NH₄ used as macronutrient by green plants are also affected by thermal–stress. Prolonged heat–stress accelerates nitrogen accumulation in the meristematic cells of the plant plays important role in energy metabolism, protein synthesis, and photosynthesis (Radecker, et al., 2022). Several microbes have been identified to mitigate heat stress by enhancing nitrogen fixation. Furthermore, symbiont relationship of plants with nitrogen fixating microbes improve the soil nitrogen concentration, rhizobacterial population levels, soil nitrogenase activities and nitrogen uptake by plants (Moynihan, et al., 2022).

ACC-deaminase is 1-Aminocyclopropane-1-carboxylate enzyme produce by some microbes accelerate plant growth by sequestering and splitting plant-produced ACC, producing alfa-ketobutyrate and ammonia. Plant–microbial interaction promotes production of ACC-deaminase, which moderated ethylene metabolism and resulted in better heat tolerance (Singh, et al., 2022). Diverse groups of microbes enhance thermal–stress in various crop species are given in the table.

Table: Microbial thermal response on various plant species

<i>Host Crops</i>	<i>Symbiont Microbes</i>	<i>Response under thermal–stress</i>	<i>References</i>
Wheat	<i>Bacillus amyloliquefaciens</i> (Bacteria)	<i>B. amyloliquefaciens</i> (UCMB5113) improved heat stress tolerance by reducing ROS and transcript level.	Abd El-Daim et al., (2014)
	<i>Bacillus amyloliquefaciens</i> (Bacteria)	Enhanced heat tolerance by modifications in wheat leaf transcript.	Abd El-Daim, et al., (2018)

	<i>B. velezensis</i> (Bacteria)	<i>B. velezensis</i> (5113) regulate metabolic pathways of amino acids, proteins to develop heat tolerance.	Abd El-Daim, et al., (2019)
	<i>P. putida</i> (Bacteria)	<i>P. putida</i> (AKMP7) increased vegetative growth, dry biomass, chlorophyll, sugars, proline, starch, amino acids under heat stress.	Ali, et al., (2011)
	Arbuscularmycorrhizal(Fungi)	AMF increased grain number in wheat plants, alters nutrient allocation and tiller number composition in the plants under heat-stress.	Cabral, et al., (2016)
Durum wheat	Endophytic Ascomycetousmitosporic fungi	Improved the hydrothermal time (HTT) and energy of germination (EG) value to enhanced resistance in heat stress.	Hubbard, et al., (2012)
		Improve photosystem II in wheat plants during vegetative growth.	Hubbard, et al., (2014)
Sorghum	<i>Pseudomonas</i> sp. (Bacteria)	<i>Pseudomonas</i> sp. strain AKM-P6 enhanced tolerance of sorghum seedlings.	Ali, et al., (2009)
	<i>B. cereus</i> , <i>Providenciarettgeri</i> , <i>M. odoratimimus</i> (Bacteria)	Increased plant growth, antioxidant, enzyme activities and decreased proline, contents in plants under heat stress and enhanced heat tolerance.	Bruno, et al., (2020)
Cucumber	Theromophilic endophytic fungus	Increased thermal–tolerance stress by maximizing quantum efficiency of photosystem II, photosynthesis rate, and water use efficiency.	Ali, et al., (2018)
<i>Cullen plicata</i>	<i>Thermomyceslanuginosus</i> (Endophytic fungus)	Enhanced heat stress tolerance by changing secondary metabolite accumulations and antioxidant activities.	Ali, et al., (2019)
Tomato	<i>S. deserticola</i> and <i>S. constrictum</i>	Reduced oxidative stress by decreasing lipid peroxidation, H ₂ O ₂ levels and enhancing antioxidant enzyme activities.	Duc, et al., (2018)
	<i>Paraburkholderiaphytifirmans</i> (Bacteria)	Improved tomato growth by enhancing chlorophyll content, accumulations of sugars, amino acids, proline, and malate.	Issa, et al., (2018)
	<i>B. cereus</i> (Bacteria)	Protect tomato seedlings against heat stress by balancing ABA, SA, APX, GSH, SOD, Fe, P, and K.	Khan, et al., (2020a)
Perennial ryegrass	<i>Epichlofestucae</i> (Endophytic fungus)	The endophyte strain AR37 synthesized alkaloids at high temperature and increase tolerance level	Hennessy, et al., (2016)
	<i>A. flavus</i> (Endophytic fungus)	Regulate concentration of ABA, proline, phenols, flavonoids, catalase and ascorbic acid oxidase against heat stress.	Ismail, et al., (2019)
	<i>A. niger</i> (Endophytic fungus)	<i>A. niger</i> protected plants from thermal stress by increasing biomass and chlorophyll content, AAO, CAT, GR, SOD, POD, proline and phenolics.	Ismail, et al., (2020a)
	<i>A. violaceofuscus</i> (Endophytic fungus)	Increased the total chlorophyll content, ROS, ABA, and proline.	Ismail, et al., (2020b)

	<i>Rhizopus oryzae</i> (Endophytic fungus)	<i>R. oryzae</i> , isolated from <i>A. capillus-veneris</i> improve heat tolerance by inducing phenolics, flavonoids, SA, IAA, AAO, CAT, proline, sugar, lipids.	Ismail, et al., (2020c)
Pipper	<i>Penicillium resedanum</i> (Endophytic fungus)	<i>P. resedanum</i> (LK6) increased the shoot length, shoot fresh and dry weights of <i>C. annuum</i> L. under heat stress.	Khan, et al., (2013)
	<i>P. resedanum</i> (Endophytic fungus)	<i>P. resedanum</i> (LK6) improved plant height and dry weight under heat stress	Khan, et al. (2015)
<i>Crocus sativus</i>	<i>Exophiala</i> sp. (LHL08) (Endophytic fungus)	Modulate heat stress by influencing physio-biochemical traits under thermal-stress.	Khan, et al., (2012b)
	<i>Paecilomycesformosus</i> (LHL10) (Endophytic fungus)	<i>P. formosus</i> (LHL10) improved growth chlorophyll contents under stress conditions.	Khan, et al. (2012a)
Soybean	<i>B. cereus</i> (Bacteria)	Mitigate heat-stress by synthesizing GA, IAA, ABA, and SA.	Khan, et al. (2012b)
Ryegrass	<i>A. aculeatus</i> (Endophytic fungus)	Improved heat tolerance by enhancing photosynthetic apparatus in heat stress	Li, et al. (2021)
Maize	<i>Glomus</i> sp.	Alter PSII h under high temperature and protect plants.	MathurandJajoo (2020)
Tomato	<i>B. cereus</i> (Bacteria)	Promoted shoot, root length, leaf surface area, fresh and dry under heat stress	Mukhtar, et al. (2020)
Rice	<i>Chaetomium</i> sp. (Fungus)	Increased roots and shoot growth under heat stress.	Sangamesh, et al. (2018)
Wheat	<i>B. safensis</i> and <i>Ochrobactrum pseudogrignonense</i> (Bacteria)	PGPR enhanced thermo-tolerance by reduction of ROS production, cellular damage, enhanced chlorophyll content, and accumulation of osmolytes.	Sarkar, et al. (2018)
<i>Arabidopsis thaliana</i>	<i>Enterobacter</i> sp. (E. bacterium)	SA187 enhanced the expression of heat-responsive genes.	Shekhawat, et al. (2020)
Rice	<i>P. formosus</i> (Endophytic fungus)	<i>P. formosus</i> LWL1formed hormones and secondary metabolites in Dongjin Japanese rice.	Waqas, et al. (2015)
Maize	<i>G. etunicatum</i> (AM fungus)	Maize plants inoculated by AM fungus performing better in terms of stomatal conductance and transpiration.	Zhu, et al. (2011)

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